

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The effectiveness of biodiversity offsetting for wild pollinator conservation

Klara Leander Oh

Plant Ecology and Nature Conservation
Group, Wageningen University &
Research, Wageningen, PB, The
Netherlands

Correspondence

Klara Leander Oh

Email: klara.leanderoh@proton.me**Funding information**

H2020 Societal Challenges, Grant/Award
Number: 101003476

Handling Editor: Patricia Landaverde
González

Abstract

1. Biodiversity offsetting, the last step in the mitigation hierarchy and part of the European Union's No Net Loss policy, has been identified as an important conservation tool. The effectiveness of offsetting for biodiversity conservation is highly variable and currently unquantified for wild pollinators, which are at risk in the EU due to land use change. Halting their decline requires at the very least no further loss of habitat, which biodiversity offsetting has the as-yet-unknown possibility to provide.
2. This study compared semi-natural grassland offsets and paired positive reference grasslands located across the Netherlands using transect walks, flower counts and vegetation surveys. We assessed wild bee and hoverfly abundances, species richness and community composition, and examined the species richness and community composition of floral resources and vegetation. Additionally, we examined whether offset age, management, prior land use and area influenced offset effectiveness.
3. Results showed significantly higher wild bee abundance and species richness in offset grasslands, while hoverflies exhibited no clear pattern. Wild bee and hoverfly community compositions were similar between site types. We found no differences in floral resources or vegetation species richness between offset and positive reference grasslands but did find differences in flower and vegetation community compositions. There were no moderating effects of site characteristics on the effectiveness of biodiversity offsetting, though prior land use did have a significant effect on wild bees, with abundances being higher in sites previously used as grassland.
4. *Policy implications.* We show that even small differences in the composition of floral resources can result in significantly higher wild pollinator abundances and species richness in offset grasslands. Since our reference grasslands represent the target habitat, our findings suggest that biodiversity offsetting of semi-natural grassland shows promise for achieving No Net Loss, and even Net Gain, of wild bee and hoverfly abundance and species richness in the Netherlands, while maintaining similar species community compositions. Biodiversity offsetting, if properly implemented, can be an effective tool for pollinator conservation.

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2026 The Author(s). *Journal of Applied Ecology* published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd on behalf of British Ecological Society.

KEYWORDS

biodiversity offsetting, community composition, land use change, no net loss, pollinator conservation, species diversity

1 | INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity offsetting has been proposed as a tool for achieving 'No Net Loss' (NNL) biodiversity objectives by conserving nature while allowing for continued development (Tucker et al., 2020). This is particularly relevant for the European Union, which has identified biodiversity offsetting as a key instrument of Target 2 of the EU 2020 Biodiversity Strategy (maintain and restore ecosystems), with the initial goal of achieving NNL of biodiversity by 2020 (European Commission, 2011) and now by 2030 (Tucker et al., 2020). Biodiversity offsets are measurable conservation and restoration outcomes designed to compensate for the adverse and unavoidable impacts of development (Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme [BBOP], 2012). Offsetting is the last step in the mitigation hierarchy, once it has been determined that avoidance, minimisation and remediation of development impacts are not sufficient (BBOP, 2012; Bull et al., 2016). The potential of offsetting to allow for infrastructure development while adhering to the conservation policy principle of NNL has promoted the uptake of offsetting policies among several countries in the EU beyond the Natura 2000 network (Bull et al., 2018; Wende et al., 2018).

In the EU, there is clear guidance on the integration of ecosystems and their services into offsetting decision-making, which provides a comprehensive, general framework for offsetting implementation. Offsets should be measurable and appropriately implemented, monitored, evaluated and enforced. Ideally, they should also account for the direct, indirect and cumulative impacts of development, across both space and time (BBOP, 2012; Tucker et al., 2020). However, our understanding of whether offsetting effectively conserves or promotes biodiversity is limited (Josefsson et al., 2021). While some publications suggest that offset projects may have the capacity to compensate for biodiversity loss (OECD, 2016; Tucker et al., 2020), the success of existing offsets is highly variable (zu Ermgassen et al., 2019).

The assessment of the effectiveness of offsetting for achieving NNL is limited, particularly due to a lack of transparency in the specification, implementation and monitoring of offset projects (Bull et al., 2018; Marshall et al., 2024). Recent global reviews have highlighted the lack of evidence supporting the potential of offset sites to compensate for development-associated losses of biodiversity, thus questioning the effectiveness of offsetting as a conservation strategy (Josefsson et al., 2021; zu Ermgassen et al., 2019). Offset outcomes are seldom reported: in a global review, zu Ermgassen et al. (2019) found only ten peer-reviewed studies reporting the biodiversity outcomes (including habitat area) of 26 individual biodiversity offsets. Of these, only four individual offsets were from Europe, and only one achieved NNL. Further, the success or effectiveness of offsets is typically measured in

terms of habitats: over 50% of guidelines recommended use habitat type, condition and area as a proxy for assessing biodiversity (Marshall et al., 2024). As a result, important dimensions of actual biodiversity can be overlooked when assessing whether an offset is considered effective.

Less is known about the effectiveness of biodiversity offsetting for invertebrates, who represent a highly important component of biodiversity. Invertebrates provide, among many other ecosystem services, the highly valuable service of crop pollination (Rader et al., 2016). In Europe, wild bees and hoverflies are important provisioners of this service (Doyle et al., 2020), yet their populations continue to decline as a result of land use and management change, such as agricultural intensification and agricultural land abandonment (Dicks et al., 2021). Halting this decline requires at the very least no further loss of their habitat. Biodiversity offsetting provides an opportunity for NNL of critical wild pollinator habitats—such as semi-natural grassland—when protected nature is developed. Semi-natural grassland is an important habitat for wild pollinators in the Netherlands (Ozinga et al., 2018), and Dutch semi-natural grasslands were in serious decline between 1900 and 2012, with over 90% of total area lost (Compendium voor de Leefomgeving, 2017). Further loss of this habitat due to infrastructure development could have serious consequences for wild pollinator populations. While wild pollinators have been found to respond positively to grassland restoration (Tonietto & Larkin, 2018), the effect of grassland restoration on wild pollinators within an offsetting framework has yet to be assessed (Josefsson et al., 2021). Moreover, the effectiveness of offsetting in grasslands is generally not well understood, with a meta-analysis finding only one study that assessed grassland offsets (Josefsson et al., 2021).

The decline of wild pollinator species across Europe highlights the need for novel and effective conservation approaches to not only halt said decline but potentially reverse it. Here, we examined the effectiveness of offsetting as a conservation instrument targeting pollinators. To this end, we conducted an experimental study in the Netherlands, where biodiversity offsetting has had a long history as a part of national conservation policy (Wende et al., 2018). The success of an offset is ideally evaluated by comparing it to a baseline, such as the biodiversity of the damaged site (Josefsson et al., 2020). As baseline data were either inaccessible or not collected for our taxa of interest, we chose to compare our chosen offsets to positive reference sites in a space-for-time substitution study design. These positive reference sites represent the end-goal of the offset sites: a like-for-like replacement of the site that was damaged. In our study design, 'successful' offsets were defined as *not* having significantly lower pollinator numbers and species richness than the positive references.

We evaluated the effectiveness of existing biodiversity offsets in supporting wild pollinator communities by comparing wild

bee, hoverfly, flowering plant and herbaceous plant populations of known offset sites to positive reference sites, focusing on semi-natural grasslands. We sought to address the following question: What is the ecological effectiveness of biodiversity offsetting for maintaining diverse wild pollinator communities in grassland habitats? We additionally explored how biodiversity offset sites compare to positive reference grasslands in terms of floral resources and herbaceous plant species richness, as wild pollinators are often responsive to changes in vegetation composition (Schaffers et al., 2008). Because communities can be similar in abundance and species richness, but still differ in composition, we also included wild bee, hoverfly, flower and vegetation community compositions in our evaluation of biodiversity offsetting. Finally, as the effectiveness of offsetting might be affected by local site characteristics, we examined whether and how the effect of offsetting was influenced by site management, prior land use, soil type, age and area.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Study design

We selected twenty offset sites based on the following criteria:

1. The habitat type fell under the following categories listed in the Dutch Nature and Landscape Index (BIJ12): N10 (wet nutrient-poor grasslands), N11 (dry nutrient-poor grasslands) and N12 (species-rich grasslands and arable land).
2. The restoration or creation of this habitat occurred under national acts or decrees with nature compensation requirements (i.e. could be defined as offsetting).
3. The site was designated as a compensation site for a specific development project and could not be part of a compensation pool or bank. Compensation pools are created for an unknown future impact and cannot be linked to the damaged habitat type used to define the reference site.
4. It was possible to determine what habitat type was lost due to development and if the offset was explicitly intended to offset that loss for the purposes of selecting appropriate reference sites.

This resulted in seventeen N12 (habitat classification: flora- and fauna-rich grassland (N12.02)) and three N10 offset sites (habitat classifications: wet meadows (N10.01) and wet hayfields (N10.02)). No suitable offset sites with the N11 habitat type could be selected. The selected offset sites were then paired to positive reference sites by matching the habitat type, soil type and landscape composition (2km buffer) of offset sites with those of nature conservation areas managed by the governmental conservation organisation *Staatsbosbeheer*. The methodology used to select reference sites can be found in the Supplement (Site selection). In total, we selected 20 biodiversity offset grasslands and 20 paired reference grasslands located in southern and eastern parts of the Netherlands (Figure 1, Table S1).

2.2 | Data collection

Permits and ethical approval were not required for data collection. Permission to access sites was granted by land owners.

2.2.1 | Pollinator sampling

Wild bees and hoverflies were sampled using standard transect walks during three survey rounds in the period May–August 2022 with approximately 10 days between rounds 1 and 2, and 14 days between rounds 2 and 3. In each site, wild bees and hoverflies were sampled in two 150m × 1m transects (Scheper et al., 2015), where individuals were caught when seen on the transect. Each transect was divided into three sub-transects of 50 m² to facilitate evenly distributed sampling, which were sampled for 5 min each, amounting to 15 min of pure sampling time per transect per survey round. Within sites, the two transects were located in representative locations (avoiding the edges) where flowers could be found and were at least 25m apart from each other. Sampling only occurred under dry weather conditions where minimum temperatures equalled or exceeded 15°C and under wind speeds less than Beaufort 5. Paired sites were visited on the same day to ensure similar site conditions. Specimens were identified on the wing when possible and otherwise were caught and later identified using *Bijen - Veldgids voor Nederland en Vlaanderen* (Falk, 2020) and *Hoverflies of Northwest Europe* (van Veen, 2010).

2.2.2 | Floral resource surveys

In the same visit as the pollinator sampling, total forb flower species richness and cover of both 150 m² transects was estimated by counting the number of floral units of each species that was in flower during the survey. A floral unit was defined as a single flower. In the case of composite and umbelliferous flowers, the entire flower head or umbel was considered to be one floral unit. The size of floral units (diameter in mm) was measured using a ruler. Transect-level flower cover was calculated by multiplying the average floral unit diameter per number of floral units per species (Scheper et al., 2015).

2.2.3 | Vegetation surveys

Vegetation was surveyed once in each site during the field season using ten 0.5m × 0.5m quadrats (2.5m² in total). These quadrats were placed randomly in the site within 100m of, but not overlapping, the transects. Each quadrat was surveyed for a total species list of vascular plants. The percent cover of each species, as well as bare ground, was assessed by the surveyor by eye from above (bird's eye view), adding up to 100%.

FIGURE 1 Map of the study sites in The Netherlands, with biodiversity offset sites shown as circles and positive reference sites as triangles. Paired sites are indicated by colour and labelled with their pair ID. Land use data for this map was acquired from TOP100NL (CC BY 4.0).

2.2.4 | Site characteristics

Information on site history and long-term management was collected from the contact person for each site regarding (1) the age of the site from establishment (i.e. when restoration and/or management were first implemented) and (2) the dominant type of management for the past 5 years and (3) land use prior to establishment. Management data included information on mowing or grazing regime and site managers additionally indicated, if known, which one-time restoration actions were taken when the site was established, such as topsoil removal and/or introducing cuttings from species-rich donor sites. Details on site characteristics can be found in the Supplement (Site Characteristics; [Table S1](#)).

2.3 | Statistical analysis

Data available from Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17464760> (Leander Oh et al., 2025). Wild bees (solitary bees and bumblebees but excluding honeybees) and hoverflies were analysed

separately. Wild pollinator abundances and species richness were pooled across transects (sum) and rounds (mean) before analysis. Site-level flower cover per site (%) was calculated by summing flower cover over the two transects, dividing by 300 m² and multiplying by 100 and averaging across rounds. Flower species richness was summed across transects and averaged across rounds. We averaged wild pollinator and floral responses across rounds, as we were not interested in exploring the seasonal effects of sampling period. Vegetation species richness was averaged across quadrats for each site. All responses were modelled using linear mixed-effect models with Pair ID as a random effect to account for the paired study design, and all sites were included in this analysis (N = 40).

Prior to the community composition analyses, vegetation, flower and pollinator communities were converted to Bray–Curtis distance matrices and scaled to relative species abundance. Three sites (no. 4, no. 21, no. 25) had no wild bee observations and were thus excluded from the analyses of wild bee community composition. Additionally, the wild bee community of site 22 was identified as an outlier and removed before analysis as it contained only one observation of a species (*Andrena labiata*) that was not present in any other site.

2.3.1 | Effectiveness of biodiversity offsetting

The effectiveness of offsetting was assessed by comparing all response variables between all paired positive reference and offset sites ($N=40$), using site type (reference versus offset) as a fixed factor. Wild bee abundance, hoverfly abundance and flower cover were $\ln(x+1)$ transformed to meet model assumptions. We then compared wild bee, hoverfly, flower and vegetation community composition between reference and offset sites ($N_{\text{wild bee}}=36$, $N_{\text{hoverfly}}=40$, $N_{\text{flower}}=40$, $N_{\text{vegetation}}=40$) using PERMANOVA analyses (Anderson, 2001) and visualised differences in community compositions using non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS).

2.3.2 | Moderating effect of site characteristics on offsetting effectiveness

For the subset of sites for which this information was available ($N=26$), we assessed the moderating effects of site characteristics (site age (years), site area (ha), soil type, site management (mowing and/or grazing) and land use prior to site conversion to an offset on the same response variables). Full global models, including all predictor variables, were defined for each response variable (Table S2). Numerical predictor variables (site age, site area) were standardised (centred and divided by two standard deviations). Model assumptions were checked for each global model. Wild bee abundance, hoverfly abundance and flower cover were first $\ln(x+1)$ transformed. We conducted all subsets regressions, limiting the number of predictors that could be included in a model subset to two (including the two-way interaction between site type and the different site characteristics) to avoid overparametrisation. The best-fitting models ($\Delta\text{AICc} \leq 2$) were averaged to determine the overall effect of the selected explanatory variables on each response.

2.3.3 | Further analyses

The vegetation quadrats included estimates of percent cover of bare ground. As bare ground can provide important nesting habitat, particularly for wild bees (Antoine & Forrest, 2021), we tested for differences in the percent cover of bare ground between site types. We then analysed the effects of flower cover, flower species richness, vegetation species richness and percent cover of bare ground on wild bee and hoverfly abundance and species richness ($N=40$ for all response variables). See more details in Supplement (Analyses; Table S3).

All analyses were done in R version 4.2.3 (R Core Team, 2023). Packages used can be found in the Supplement (R Packages).

3 | RESULTS

Eleven biodiversity offset sites and paired control sites were located on sandy soils (the most common soil type in the Netherlands), seven

on sandy loam soils and two on clay soils. Offset sites ranged in area from 0.7 to 110.0 ha (mean \pm SE: 13.0 ± 24.4 ha) and in age from 1 to 24 years (8.0 ± 5.2 years). Positive reference sites ranged in area from 0.3 to 49.1 ha (13.4 ± 13.7 ha) and in age from 4 to 100 years (34.8 ± 25.8 years). We sampled a total of 2128 hoverflies (66 species), 799 bumblebees (8 species) and 192 other wild bees (37 species). The five most common pollinator species were *Eristalis tenax* ($n=703$), *Bombus pascuorum* ($n=410$), *Bombus lapidarius* ($n=239$), *Episyrphus balteatus* ($n=198$) and *Sphaerophoria scripta* ($n=127$). We counted 215 species of herbaceous plants. *Trifolium repens* (64.5%), *Cerastium fontanum* (51.5%), *Trifolium pratense* (48.5%), *Ranunculus acris* (46%) and *Ranunculus repens* (44%) were the top five flowering plant species by frequency of occurrence within transects. Across positive reference and offset sites, sampling completeness ranged from 79 to 89% for all response variables (Figure S1, Table S4). Lists of all pollinator and plant species can be found in Data S2.

3.1 | Floral resources and vegetation

We found no significant differences between offset and positive reference sites in terms of flower species richness ($\chi^2(1)=2.493$, $p=0.114$) or vegetation species richness ($\chi^2(1)=0.251$, $p=0.617$), though there was a trend of higher flower cover in offset sites ($\chi^2(1)=3.193$, $p=0.074$). The mean values for all flower and vegetation metrics also tended to be higher in offset sites, though this difference was not significant (Figure 2; Table S5).

3.2 | Pollinators

Wild bee abundance and species richness differed consistently between offset and positive reference sites (Figure 3, Table S6). Wild bee abundance in offset sites was more than twice as high as in reference sites, with a mean of 7.7 (SE=0.188) wild bees in offsets compared to 3.8 (SE=0.188) wild bees in references (Figure 3a, $\chi^2(1)=4.551$, $p=0.033$). Offset sites also had on average higher wild bee species richness (Figure 3b, $\chi^2(1)=3.84$, $p=0.050$). Hoverfly abundance and species richness were generally higher in offset sites compared to reference grasslands, but the difference was not statistically significant (Abundance: Figure 3c, $\chi^2(1)=3.615$, $p=0.057$; Species richness: Figure 3d, $\chi^2(1)=3.555$, $p=0.059$).

3.3 | Community composition

Group variances were homogeneous for all communities excluding hoverflies (Table S7). As such, we can confidently assess the effect of site type on flower, vegetation and wild bee communities (Warton et al., 2012). We found that the composition of both vegetation and flower communities differed significantly between positive reference and offset sites (Figure 4a,b). Site type represented

FIGURE 2 Predicted values and 95% confidence intervals of (a) flower species richness, (b) vegetation species richness and (c) flower cover, adjusted for the random effect of site pair ID. Flower cover is back-transformed to the original response scale. Flower species richness is measured per 300m² and vegetation species richness per 0.25m². Transparent points are partial residuals. * $p < 0.05$, n.s., not significant.

FIGURE 3 Predicted values and 95% confidence intervals of (a) wild bee abundance, (b) hoverfly abundance, (c) wild bee species richness, (d) hoverfly species richness, adjusted for the random effect of site pair ID. Wild bee and hoverfly abundance are back-transformed to the original response scale. Transparent points are partial residuals. * $p < 0.05$, n.s., not significant.

4.8% of variation in vegetation community composition ($F(1)=1.982$, $R^2=0.046$, $p=0.004$) and 5.6% of variation in flower community composition ($F(1)=2.247$, $R^2=0.056$, $p=0.003$). Wild bee and hoverfly communities were found to be the same between site types (Figure 4c,d). For all communities, between 94 to 98% of variation across sites was unaccounted for (Table S8).

3.4 | Site characteristics

We found little support for moderating influences of site characteristics on the effects of offsetting (minimal support for interaction effects; Table S9). Only prior land use was a strong predictor of wild bee species richness (Table 1, Figure S2). Wild bee species richness

FIGURE 4 Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plot of (a) vegetation, (b) flower, (c) wild bee and (d) hoverfly communities. Communities are grouped by site type (yellow = positive reference, green = offset). Coloured points represent sites. The five highest abundance or cover estimates for each community (wild bees, hoverflies = abundance; flowers, vegetation = percent cover) are indicated by black points. Points located near offset sites were more associated with that site type and vice versa. k = the total number of dimensions; stress = an indicator of goodness of fit.

was 1.5 times higher when an offset site had been grassland prior to establishment, compared to cropland (Figure S3). Site type was no longer a strong predictor of wild bee species richness. No predictors relating to management, prior land use, site area or soil type featured in the best subset models for hoverflies (Table S9). Site age featured inconsistently in the model sets and when present was a weak predictor of wild pollinator abundance and species richness (Table 1, Table S9). Wild pollinator abundance and species richness were instead strongly related to percent flower cover and flower species richness (Table S10).

Floral resources and vegetation were similarly not strongly predicted by any site characteristics (Table 2, Figure S4). Site type, age, area, management and soil type featured inconsistently in the floral resource models (Table S9) and were overall weak predictors of flower cover and species richness. Vegetation species richness was ultimately best explained by an intercept-only model.

3.5 | Links between pollinators, floral resources and bare ground

We found a trend of higher proportions of bare ground in the offset sites compared to positive references ($\chi^2(1) = 3.531$, $p = 0.060$). However, wild pollinator abundance and species richness were not strongly predicted by the proportion of bare ground when it was included in a model alongside floral resources and vegetation species richness (Table S10). Floral resources alone were consistent, strong predictors for both wild bee and hoverfly abundance and species richness (Table S10, Figures S5 and S6).

4 | DISCUSSION

Our study represents one of the first evaluations of biodiversity offsetting as a tool for halting wild pollinator decline. We found that,

TABLE 1 Full model-averaged coefficients of wild bee and hoverfly response variables. Brackets contain the 95% confidence intervals.

	Wild bees		Hoverflies	
	Abundance	Spp. richness	Abundance	Spp. richness
Site type (Offset)	0.76 [0.11, 1.42]	0.39 [-0.52, 1.31]	0.38 [-0.61, 1.37]	1.36 [-1.06, 3.79]
Age	-0.16 [-0.90, 0.59]	-0.09 [-0.68, 0.51]	-0.20 [-1.20, 0.80]	-1.14 [-4.41, 2.12]
PLU (Grassland)		1.52 [0.30, 2.75]		0.16 [-0.97, 1.29]
PLU (Other)		-0.42 [-1.77, 0.93]		-0.36 [-2.52, 1.79]
Age × site type (Offset)			-0.19 [-1.42, 1.04]	
PLU (Grassland) × site type (Offset)		-0.63 [-2.58, 1.31]		-0.19 [-1.48, 1.10]
PLU (Other) × site type (Offset)		0.14 [-1.11, 1.38]		1.12 [-4.25, 6.49]

Note: Cells are empty where a predictor was not included in the final averaged model. Coefficients where the 95% confidence interval did not intersect 0 are bolded. Wild bee and hoverfly abundance are $\ln(x + 1)$ transformed. Categorical reference levels (intercepts): Site type (Positive reference), PLU (Cropland). All predictors not included were not part of the final candidate model sets. Age = age since establishment (years). Abbreviation: PLU, prior land use.

TABLE 2 Full model-averaged coefficients of flower and vegetation response variables.

	Flowers		Vegetation
	Cover (%)	Spp. richness	Spp. richness
Intercept	0.29 [0.05, 0.52]	11.66 [6.98, 16.35]	6.38 [5.29, 7.46]
Site type (Offset)	0.16 [-0.29, 0.61]	0.96 [-3.09, 5.01]	
Age	0.03 [-0.31, 0.37]	-0.66 [-5.31, 3.99]	
Age × site type (Offset)	-0.22 [-0.95, 0.51]		
Area	-0.03 [-0.22, 0.17]		
Management (Grazing)		-0.68 [-4.73, 3.37]	
Management (Mowing)		0.48 [-2.68, 3.64]	
Soil type (Sand)		-0.42 [-3.30, 2.47]	

Note: Brackets contain the 95% confidence intervals. Cells are empty where a predictor was not included in the final averaged model. Flower cover is $\ln(x + 1)$ transformed. Categorical reference levels (intercepts): Site type (Positive reference), Management (both grazing and mowing), Soil type (Clay). All predictors not included were not part of the final candidate model sets. Area = total site area (ha), Age = age since establishment (years).

compared to positive reference sites representative of the grasslands that were lost, offset sites had similar plant species richness and floral resources, but the composition of the vegetation was significantly different. The investigated offset sites were established by a variety of approaches, such as topsoil removal, introducing cuttings with seeds from donor sites or merely cessation of the application of agrochemical inputs. In response to the new site conditions and/or management regime, the vegetation of offset sites is expected to transition towards the reference vegetation type, a process that may take many decades (Silvertown et al., 2006). Offset sites, which were generally younger (average age = 7.9 years), had a stronger representation of a species that is light-demanding and well-adapted to grazing, such as *Trifolium repens* (Figure 4a; Burdon, 1983). Positive reference sites (average age = 34.8 years) had a stronger representation of tall dominant grasses such as *Holcus lanatus* and *Agrostis capillaris* that do better under the more extensive grazing or mowing management (Beddows, 1961) that are typically implemented in protected areas.

Differences in flower composition may explain why we found significantly higher wild bee richness and abundance in offset sites, even though flower richness and cover were similar. Offset sites may

have had higher cover and richness of the flower species preferred by wild bees (i.e. *T. repens* and *Lotus pedunculatus*). Bumblebees have been found to mainly respond to the cover of Fabaceae species but not of other plant families (Scheper et al., 2021) and even individual bumblebee species can exhibit strong differences in preferences for certain flower species (Kleijn & Raemakers, 2008). Additional factors may have further contributed to the higher value of offset sites such as the availability of bare soil, which provides important nesting habitat for many species (Antoine & Forrest, 2021). The cover of bare soil tended to be higher in offset sites, but our analyses showed that there was no significant relationship with bee abundance or species richness. The less pronounced differences in hoverfly abundance and species richness between offset and positive reference sites could similarly be because the flower species they generally are most strongly related to (in the Netherlands, Apiaceae; Scheper et al., 2021) differed less strongly between the two site types, though we did not specifically test this. Additionally, we do not expect there were differences between site types in aphids and eutrophic water bodies, the larval resources of the most commonly encountered hoverfly species (Hall & Gerhardt, 2002).

We found little evidence that site characteristics moderate the effect of site type on wild pollinator species richness or abundance. This is not surprising, as we also did not find an interactive effect on vegetation and flowers, and we expect any effects on wild bees and hoverflies to operate through effects on vegetation and flowers. Instead, pollinator foraging ranges may play a role. While neighbouring sites were sufficiently far apart to be spatially independent (minimum of 1.53 km and on average 8.52 ± 6.06 km) given the typical foraging ranges of wild bees and hoverflies (150–1500 m; Gathmann & Tscharntke, 2002; Greenleaf et al., 2007; Kleijn & van Langevelde, 2006; Meyer et al., 2009; Redhead et al., 2016; Zurbuchen et al., 2010), it is still possible that many of the pollinators we observed originated from the landscape surrounding the study sites and used the sites predominantly for foraging. Hoverflies are not bound to a nest site and can disperse freely through the landscape (Ekroos et al., 2013). Bumblebees are bound to a nest but can have relatively large foraging ranges (Redhead et al., 2016) that exceed the size of the studied sites. While solitary bees may have originated from within sites as they have smaller foraging ranges than bumblebees (Greenleaf et al., 2007), they also made up a far smaller proportion of the sampled wild bee population in both offset (17.4% of total wild bee abundance) and positive reference sites (30.4%). Consequently, their influence on the results was likely minimal. Additionally, because we ensured that landscape habitat composition and soil type were similar between pairs of sites, the landscape-level species pools were probably similar. Wild bee species richness was the only pollinator variable that was strongly predicted by a site characteristic, irrespective of whether it was an offset or positive reference. Sites that had been used as grassland (i.e. meadow or pasture) before conversion to a semi-natural grassland had on average 1.5 times more wild bee species than sites that had previously been cropland. In contrast to Dutch cropland, grasslands may provide nesting habitats for solitary bees, of which many species have a limited foraging range and may be more strongly influenced by site-level nesting availability than bumblebees or hoverflies (Gathmann & Tscharntke, 2002). Ultimately, our results indicate that the usage and importance of offset sites to wild bees and hoverflies is largely determined by the availability and composition of floral resources. This is in line with literature that show the strong relationships between wild pollinators and flowers (Bishop et al., 2024; Scheper et al., 2015) and that wild pollinator abundance and species richness often benefit from improved management and restoration interventions in grasslands (Tonietto & Larkin, 2018).

A limitation of our study is that it uses a space-for-time design that assumes that our controls were equivalent to the sites that were destroyed (Kujala et al., 2022). This approach was necessary because biodiversity data on sites affected by development projects is generally not available or sufficiently comprehensive. However, we believe this approach is acceptable as there is no reason to assume that the sites that were destroyed were inherently of higher nature-value than the average nature reserve with the same grassland type. Another limitation is that we only assessed offset sites that had successfully been established (i.e. we knew that changes to management, and potentially one-time restoration actions, had occurred, regardless of

whether the target vegetation community was achieved) and were still present at the time of the study. Significant uncertainty surrounds how often offsetting is actually implemented as part of policy requirements (e.g. within the EU Habitats Directive or Dutch Nature Conservation Act). Even for countries that have comprehensive frameworks for offsetting, little is known about how often required offsetting is actually implemented, how such sites are managed, and whether they are there, and of good quality, several years after establishment (Bull et al., 2018). This uncertainty can be addressed by more transparent reporting of what has been done in terms of offsetting following developments that negatively affect biodiversity (Maron et al., 2016). Yet, record keeping is generally poor for biodiversity offsetting projects (Bull et al., 2018), including those in the Netherlands, which prevents enforcing compliance to offsetting regulations by responsible authorities (Kujala et al., 2022). As such, we could only evaluate post-implementation outcomes and therefore cannot comment on the effectiveness of biodiversity offsetting as a policy instrument, as this depends on implementation. Improved record keeping would not only promote transparency in biodiversity offsetting but would also benefit future studies on the conservation effectiveness of offsetting. Similarly, the lack of any evidence that management regime had a significant effect on wild pollinator, vegetation or floral responses highlights the need for data not only on current management, but also the original restoration interventions applied to the grassland. Interventions such as topsoil removal and introducing seeds can have large positive impacts on the restoration of the plant community (Resch et al., 2019), which is likely to influence in turn the wild pollinator community (Schaffers et al., 2008). If site managers want to learn from what they are doing and improve conservation success, accurate records should be kept of how an offset site was established and how it was subsequently managed. However, in our experience this information is generally unknown or undocumented, at least in the Netherlands. Without adequate data on management, restoration actions and ecological conditions prior to habitat destruction, it can be difficult to quantify if offsets are effective, and furthermore, *why* they are effective.

Our study suggests that, when established properly, offset sites can be as good, and may initially even be better, than positive reference sites in terms of wild pollinator species richness. We used reference sites of the target ecosystems and not controls of more intensively used, lower-quality ecosystems. Similarities in biodiversity levels between the two site types (i.e. no significant differences) therefore also represent evidence of success. Significantly lower biodiversity estimates in offset compared to reference sites would have been an indication that offset sites had (thus far) failed to compensate biodiversity loss on the destroyed sites, but we did not find this. We present convincing evidence that biodiversity offsetting, if implemented well, can be an effective tool for pollinator biodiversity conservation. Our findings indicate that biodiversity offsetting sites had a subtly different composition of the plant community with higher dominance of flowering forbs and lower dominance of grasses (Figure 4a). This suggests that effective implementation is mainly determined by proper establishment (particularly the removal of fertile topsoil of

former arable land; Resch et al., 2019) and mowing frequently enough to maintaining low productive grasslands to prevent dominance of grasses that may suppress the flowering forbs that pollinators rely on for food (Figure 4a). In the Netherlands, this generally means mowing twice per year with removal of the cuttings (Bakker et al., 2024).

Future studies on offsetting could investigate other dimensions of biodiversity such as beta or gamma diversity or species-level niche optimum approaches as these may reveal different responses (Chisté et al., 2018; Tsang et al., 2025), study functional aspects using plant-pollinator networks, explore impacts on nesting sites and larval habitat availability for wild bees and hoverflies, or explore the effects that microclimate, such as light, soil moisture or slope, might have on local vegetation and floral communities.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Klara Leander Oh, David Kleijn and Jeroen Scheper conceived the ideas and designed methodology; Klara Leander Oh analysed the data; Klara Leander Oh led the writing of the manuscript. All authors contributed critically to the drafts and gave final approval for publication.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101003476 (Safeguard project). We thank Francesca Sodano, Liyenne Hagenberg and Bram de Vries for collecting the data for this study. We would also like to thank all landowners for allowing us to work on their land.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17464760> (Leander Oh et al., 2025).

STATEMENT ON INCLUSION

All authors involved in this study are based in the country where the study was carried out. Efforts were made to consider relevant work published in the local language.

ORCID

Klara Leander Oh <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6660-1218>

Jeroen Scheper <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4314-996X>

David Kleijn <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2500-7164>

REFERENCES

- Anderson, M. J. (2001). A new method for non-parametric multivariate analysis of variance. *Austral Ecology*, 26(1), 32–46. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1442-9993.2001.01070.pp.x>
- Antoine, C. M., & Forrest, J. R. K. (2021). Nesting habitat of ground-nesting bees: A review. *Ecological Entomology*, 46(2), 143–159. <https://doi.org/10.1111/een.12986>

- Bakker, W., Morel, T., Ozinga, W., Scheper, J., & Vergeer, P. (2024). The relative importance of nitrogen deposition and climate change in driving plant diversity decline in roadside grasslands. *Science of the Total Environment*, 955, 176962. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.176962>
- Beddows, A. R. (1961). *Holcus lanatus* L. *Journal of Ecology*, 49(2), 421–430. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2257274>
- Bishop, G. A., Fijen, T. P. M., Raemakers, I., van Kats, R. J. M., & Kleijn, D. (2024). Bees go up, flowers go down: Increased resource limitation from late spring to summer in agricultural landscapes. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 61(3), 431–441. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14576>
- Bull, J. W., Brauner, K., Darbi, M., Van Teeffelen, A. J. A., Quétiér, F., Brooks, S. E., Dunnett, S., & Strange, N. (2018). Data transparency regarding the implementation of European 'no net loss' biodiversity policies. *Biological Conservation*, 218, 64–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2017.12.002>
- Bull, J. W., Gordon, A., Watson, J. E. M., & Maron, M. (2016). Seeking convergence on the key concepts in 'no net loss' policy. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 53(6), 1686–1693. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12726>
- Burdon, J. J. (1983). *Trifolium Repens* L. *Journal of Ecology*, 71(1), 307–330. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2259979>
- Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme (BBOP). (2012). *Standard on biodiversity offsets*. BBOP.
- Chisté, M. N., Mody, K., Kunz, G., Gunczy, J., & Blüthgen, N. (2018). Intensive land use drives small-scale homogenization of plant- and leafhopper communities and promotes generalists. *Oecologia*, 186, 529–540. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-017-4031-0>
- Compendium voor de Leefomgeving. (2017). *Natuurareaal op het land 1900–2012*. <https://www.clo.nl/indicatoren/nl159001-natuurareaal-op-het-land-1900-2012>
- Dicks, L. V., Breeze, T. D., Ngo, H. T., Senapathi, D., An, J., Aizen, M. A., Basu, P., Buchori, D., Galetto, L., Garibaldi, L. A., Gemmill-Herren, B., Howlett, B. G., Imperatriz-Fonseca, V. L., Johnson, S. D., Kovács-Hostyánszki, A., Kwon, Y. J., Lattorff, H. M. G., Lungharwo, T., Seymour, C. L., ... Potts, S. G. (2021). A global-scale expert assessment of drivers and risks associated with pollinator decline. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 5(10), 1453–1461. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-021-01534-9>
- Doyle, T., Hawkes, W. L. S., Massy, R., Powney, G. D., Menz, M. H. M., & Wotton, K. R. (2020). Pollination by hoverflies in the Anthropocene. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 287(1927), 20200508. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2020.0508>
- Ekroos, J., Rundlöf, M., & Smith, H. G. (2013). Trait-dependent responses of flower-visiting insects to distance to semi-natural grasslands and landscape heterogeneity. *Landscape Ecology*, 28(7), 1283–1292. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-013-9864-2>
- European Commission. (2011). *Our life insurance, our natural capital: An EU biodiversity strategy to 2020: Communication from the commission to the European Parliament, the council, the European economic and social committee and the Committee of the Regions*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Falk, S. (2020). *Bijen Veldgids voor Nederland en Vlaanderen*. Kosmos Uitgevers.
- Gathmann, A., & Tschardtke, T. (2002). Foraging ranges of solitary bees. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 71(5), 757–764. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2656.2002.00641.x>
- Greenleaf, S. S., Williams, N. M., Winfree, R., & Kremen, C. (2007). Bee foraging ranges and their relationship to body size. *Oecologia*, 153(3), 589–596. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-007-0752-9>
- Hall, R. D., & Gerhardt, R. R. (2002). 8 - Flies (Diptera). In G. Mullen & L. Durden (Eds.), *Medical and veterinary entomology* (pp. 127–145). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-012510451-7/50010-4>

- Josefsson, J., Hiron, M., Arlt, D., Auffret, A. G., Berg, Å., Chevalier, M., Glimskär, A., Hartman, G., Kačergytė, I., Klein, J., Knape, J., Laugen, A. T., Low, M., Paquet, M., Pasanen-Mortensen, M., Rosin, Z. M., Rubene, D., Žmihorski, M., & Pärt, T. (2020). Improving scientific rigour in conservation evaluations and a plea deal for transparency on potential biases. *Conservation Letters*, 13(5), e12726. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12726>
- Josefsson, J., Widenfalk, L. A., Blicharska, M., Hedblom, M., Pärt, T., Ranius, T., & Öckinger, E. (2021). Compensating for lost nature values through biodiversity offsetting – Where is the evidence? *Biological Conservation*, 257, 109117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2021.109117>
- Kleijn, D., & Raemakers, I. (2008). A retrospective analysis of pollen host plant use by stable and declining bumblebee species. *Ecology*, 89(7), 1811–1823. <https://doi.org/10.1890/07-1275.1>
- Kleijn, D., & van Langevelde, F. (2006). Interacting effects of landscape context and habitat quality on flower visiting insects in agricultural landscapes. *Basic and Applied Ecology*, 7(3), 201–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2005.07.011>
- Kujala, H., Maron, M., Kennedy, C. M., Evans, M. C., Bull, J. W., Wintle, B. A., Iftekar, S. M., Selwood, K. E., Beissner, K., & Osborn, D. (2022). Credible biodiversity offsetting needs public national registers to confirm no net loss. *One Earth*, 5(6), 650–662.
- Leander Oh, K., Kleijn, D., & Scheper, J. (2025). *The effectiveness of biodiversity offsetting for wild pollinator conservation* [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17464760>
- Maron, M., Ives, C. D., Kujala, H., Bull, J. W., Maseyk, F. J. F., Bekessy, S., Gordon, A., Watson, J. E. M., Lentini, P. E., Gibbons, P., Possingham, H. P., Hobbs, R. J., Keith, D. A., Wintle, B. A., & Evans, M. C. (2016). Taming a wicked problem: Resolving controversies in biodiversity offsetting. *Bioscience*, 66(6), 489–498. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biw038>
- Marshall, E., Southwell, D., Wintle, B. A., & Kujala, H. (2024). A global analysis reveals a collective gap in the transparency of offset policies and how biodiversity is measured. *Conservation Letters*, 17(1), e12987. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12987>
- Meyer, B., Jauker, F., & Steffan-Dewenter, I. (2009). Contrasting resource-dependent responses of hoverfly richness and density to landscape structure. *Basic and Applied Ecology*, 10(2), 178–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2008.01.001>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2016). *Biodiversity offsets: Effective design and implementation*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264222519-en>
- Ozinga, W. A., Scheper, J., de Groot, G. A., Reemer, M., Raemakers, I., van Dooremalen, C., Biesmeijer, K., & Kleijn, D. (2018). Wilde bijen en zweefvliegen per landschapstype. In *WEnR report 2920*. Wageningen Environmental Research. <https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/wurpubs/544769>
- R Core Team. (2023). *R: A language and environment for statistical computing (version 4.4.1) [computer software]*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Rader, R., Bartomeus, I., Garibaldi, L. A., Garratt, M. P. D., Howlett, B. G., Winfree, R., Cunningham, S. A., Mayfield, M. M., Arthur, A. D., Andersson, G. K. S., Bommarco, R., Brittain, C., Carvalheiro, L. G., Chacoff, N. P., Entling, M. H., Foully, B., Freitas, B. M., Gemmill-Herren, B., Ghazoul, J., ... Woyciechowski, M. (2016). Non-bee insects are important contributors to global crop pollination. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 113(1), 146–151. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1517092112>
- Redhead, J. W., Dreier, S., Bourke, A. F. G., Heard, M. S., Jordan, W. C., Sumner, S., Wang, J., & Carvell, C. (2016). Effects of habitat composition and landscape structure on worker foraging distances of five bumblebee species. *Ecological Applications*, 26(3), 726–739. <https://doi.org/10.1890/15-0546>
- Resch, M. C., Schütz, M., Graf, U., Wagenaar, R., van der Putten, W. H., & Risch, A. C. (2019). Does topsoil removal in grassland restoration benefit both soil nematode and plant communities? *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 56, 1782–1793. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13400>
- Schaffers, A. P., Raemakers, I. P., Sýkora, K. V., & ter Braak, C. J. F. (2008). Arthropod assemblages are best predicted by plant species composition. *Ecology*, 89(3), 782–794. <https://doi.org/10.1890/07-0361.1>
- Scheper, J., Bommarco, R., Holzschuh, A., Potts, S. G., Riedinger, V., Roberts, S. P. M., Rundlöf, M., Smith, H. G., Steffan-Dewenter, I., Wickens, J. B., Wickens, V. J., & Kleijn, D. (2015). Local and landscape-level floral resources explain effects of wildflower strips on wild bees across four European countries. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 52(5), 1165–1175. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12479>
- Scheper, J., Bukovinsky, T., Huigens, M. E., & Kleijn, D. (2021). Attractiveness of sown wildflower strips to flower-visiting insects depends on seed mixture and establishment success. *Basic and Applied Ecology*, 56, 401–415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2021.08.014>
- Silvertown, J., Poulton, P., Johnston, E., Edwards, G., Heard, M., & Biss, P. M. (2006). The park grass experiment 1856–2006: Its contribution to ecology. *Journal of Ecology*, 94(4), 801–814. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2745.2006.01145.x>
- Tonietto, R. K., & Larkin, D. J. (2018). Habitat restoration benefits wild bees: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 55(2), 582–590. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13012>
- Tsang, T. P. N., De Santis, A. A. A., Armas-Quiñonez, G., Ascher, J. S., Ávila-Gómez, E. S., Báldi, A., Ballare, K. M., Balzan, M. V., Banaszak-Cibicka, W., Bänisch, S., Basset, Y., Bates, A. J., Baumann, J. M., Beal-Neves, M., Bennett, A., Bezerra, A. D. M., Blochtein, B., Bommarco, R., Brosi, B., ... Bonebrake, T. C. (2025). Land use change consistently reduces α - but not β - and γ -diversity of bees. *Global Change Biology*, 31(1), e70006. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.70006>
- Tucker, G., Quéfier, F., & Wende, W. (2020). *Guidance on achieving no net loss or net gain of biodiversity and ecosystem services*. Institute for European Environmental Policy.
- van Veen, M. P. (2010). *Hoverflies of Northwest Europe: Identification keys to the Syrphidae* (Second ed.). KNNV Publishing.
- Warton, D. I., Wright, S. T., & Wang, Y. (2012). Distance-based multivariate analyses confound location and dispersion effects. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 3(1), 89–101. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2041-210X.2011.00127.x>
- Wende, W., Tucker, G.-M., Quéfier, F., Rayment, M., & Darbi, M. (2018). *Biodiversity offsets: European perspectives on no net loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services*. Springer.
- zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Baker, J., Griffiths, R. A., Strange, N., Struebig, M. J., & Bull, J. W. (2019). The ecological outcomes of biodiversity offsets under “no net loss” policies: A global review. *Conservation Letters*, 12(6), e12664. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12664>
- Zurbuchen, A., Landert, L., Klaiber, J., Müller, A., Hein, S., & Dorn, S. (2010). Maximum foraging ranges in solitary bees: Only few individuals have the capability to cover long foraging distances. *Biological Conservation*, 143(3), 669–676. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2009.12.003>

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

Figure S1. Species accumulation curves for each species group, showing how the expected number of species increases with the total number of sampled positive reference (red lines) and offset sites (blue lines).

Figure S2. Model-averaged beta coefficients and 95% confidence intervals of the effects of site type and site characteristics on (A)

wild bee abundance, (B) wild bee species richness, (C) hoverfly abundance, and (D) hoverfly species richness.

Figure S3. Predicted values and 95% confidence intervals for (A) the effect of site type on wild bee abundance and (B) prior land use on wild bee species richness.

Figure S4. Model-averaged beta coefficients and 95% confidence intervals of the effects of site type and site characteristics on (A) flower cover (%), (B) flower species richness, and (C) vegetation species richness.

Figure S5. Model-averaged beta coefficients and 95% confidence intervals of the effects of flower cover (%), flower and vegetation species richness, and bare ground cover (%) on (A) wild bee abundance, (B) wild bee species richness, (C) hoverfly abundance, and (D) hoverfly species richness.

Figure S6. Predicted values and 95% confidence intervals for the effects of percent flower cover on wild bee and hoverfly abundance (A, D) and wild bee species richness (C), and flower species richness on wild bee and hoverfly abundance (B, E) and hoverfly species richness (F).

Table S1. Study site characteristics, management, and history information.

Table S2. Global model formulas for all wild pollinator, flower, and vegetation responses to the effects of site characteristics.

Table S3. Global model formulas for all wild pollinator responses to the effects of flower and bare ground cover, and flower and vegetation species richness.

Table S4. Total observed species and sampling completeness across all positive reference and offset sites for all species groups.

Table S5. Linear mixed model summaries of the effects of biodiversity offsetting on all flower and vegetation response variables.

Table S6. Linear mixed model summaries of the effects of biodiversity offsetting on all wild pollinator response variables.

Table S7. Per-community permutation tests (N permutations = 9999) of multivariate group variances for Site Type.

Table S8. Marginal effects of PERMANOVA analyses (N permutations = 9999) on the effect of site type on species communities.

Table S9. Beta coefficients and model weights of the effect of site type and site characteristics for all candidate models with a $\Delta AICc$ of ≤ 2 .

Table S10. Beta coefficients and model weights of the effects of flower and bare ground cover, and flower and vegetation species richness for all candidate models with a $\Delta AICc$ of ≤ 2 .

Data S2. Tables of all pollinator and plant species observed in the study.

How to cite this article: Leander Oh, K., Scheper, J., & Kleijn, D. (2026). The effectiveness of biodiversity offsetting for wild pollinator conservation. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 63, e70410. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.70410>